

MEDIA'S REPRESENTATION OF PAKISTANI WOMEN: EFFECTS ON GENDER ROLES AND PERCEPTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Recently, media has been an important tool as it shapes people's perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes, especially regarding gender roles and stereotypes. This study looks at how people's perceptions of gender roles are influenced by how women are portrayed in the media (especially in TV/Movies). The research will examine the nuanced facets of women's empowerment and investigate whether or not media portrayals of women inadvertently perpetuate stereotypes or help young women feel encouraged. Through a mixed-method approach, this research would try to gather insights into how media shapes the perceptions of women's empowerment and contributes to the reinforcement or challenge of prevailing gender norms. For this, a survey from college/university girls of Lahore and in-depth interviews with psychologists will be conducted. The study's conclusions shed light on the complex relationship between gender stereotypes and the media. Furthermore, this study aims to look into how media representation may affect Pakistani women's perception of their bodies and self-worth. This research aims to comprehend whether depictions of women in the media contribute to unrealistic beauty standards and cause a feeling of inadequacy among young women.

Keywords: Media representation, Women empowerment, Stereotypes, Gender norms, Societal perception.

INTRODUCTION

We are all capable of being captivated by the media's ability to effect social change. Globally, the entertainment sector is an important instrument for measuring and influencing social changes. Now, drama has emerged as a powerful medium that captivates the minds and souls of audiences. Through this, the fabric of society is not only united by it but also has its darker aspects highlighted by it. Through media, numerous sensitive issues such as domestic violence, girls' education, child labor, child abuse, divorce, incompatible couples, societal pressure on males,

and psychological problems are addressed—topics that were once considered taboo. The society and its inhabitants are not only reflected by the media but also have their political, economic, social, and psychological mindset checked by it.

While media across the globe has been utilized as a platform to promote acceptance of diversity, transcending differences of race and ethnicity, the situation in Pakistan remains somewhat different. Throughout the world, whether in the developed countries of the West or the

developing nations of the Global South, women have historically been excluded from significant roles in various spheres of life, and the media has been no exception. Women were often depicted merely as supporting characters or secondary figures. However, over time, the West recognized the importance of women as integral participants in mass media. While the West managed to acknowledge the significance of women nearly a century ago, South Asian countries, particularly Pakistan, lag by almost a century. Unfortunately, the media in Pakistan continues to be a tool for perpetuating misogynistic and other objectionable tendencies within the society. For instance, the drama 'Mere Pass Tum Ho' was highly popular but also controversial. In this drama, the female character is portrayed as materialistic, seemingly justifying male infidelity. Additionally, the male lead made several derogatory remarks, such as calling a woman "2 takay ki Aurat" (a woman worth two pennies), which are overtly misogynistic. Despite this, he was still depicted as a loving and caring husband, garnering sympathy from the audience. Similarly, in the drama 'Pyar Kay Sadkay', the male lead's childish behavior was difficult to watch, yet it was portrayed as endearing. Similarly, there are dramas where female characters are portrayed as strong or where serious social issues are raised. However, these shows often also emphasize female beauty. For example, in the drama 'Hum Kahan Kay Sachay Thay', even though the storyline was strong, there was an unnecessary emphasis on the lead actresses' fair complexion as a standard of beauty. Likewise, the drama 'Yaariyan' focused unnecessarily on the female lead's physical appearance, fashion, and styling, rather than on their personal growth. Previously, there were very few quality dramas centered around women with strong leading characters. However, over time, improvements have been observed. Dramas such as 'Zindagi Gulzar Hai', 'Yakeen Ka Safar', 'Humsafar, and 'Ehd-e-Wafa' have portrayed strong female characters with admirable capabilities, who rediscover themselves after enduring difficult times. Nevertheless, at the same time, socially established stereotypical dramas are still being produced, which further reinforce already entrenched mindsets.

Pakistani media continues to grapple with gender roles, with only a small segment of the population exhibiting an unbiased perspective on gender-related issues. Most Pakistani dramas still portray a male-dominated society, often featuring fragile female characters. Like other countries, in Pakistan, television is a source of a powerful tool to shape the narrative of the Pakistani audience, so anything discussed in the medium would have a profound impact on the audience (Ali et al. 2015). Only recently, there have been a few examples of strong female characters, but even now, women are predominantly objectified as fragile and passive. Women are often portrayed in an overly beautified manner or associated with unrealistic attributes, which not only reflects the mentality of our society but also reveals the extent to which superficial ideals influence us.

The primary objective of this article is to assess the impact of Pakistani dramas on women in Lahore. To achieve this, a survey was conducted with female students from universities and colleges in Lahore. This focus is crucial, as these educated women are still confronted with societal taboos reinforced by the portrayal in these dramas. These dramas create such irrational expectations and demands that they contribute to societal imbalances including an increase in divorce cases, a rise in sexist inclinations, and problems with compatibility between spouses. This article's goal is to investigate how educated young women view themselves about these plays' portrayals, which have sparked an odd rat race in society. In addition, this study looks at how media representations may affect Pakistani women's perceptions of their bodies and self-esteem. This investigation will assist in determining whether these portrayals uphold unrealistic beauty standards and, as a result, cause young women to feel uneasy.

Literature Review:

Many academics have long debated how women are portrayed in the media since it has a big impact on how society views gender and how people behave in terms of gender roles and self-image. In this regard, numerous researchers in Western media have explored the roles of women and how societal perceptions affect them (Douglas, 1995; Tuchman, 2000; (Kilbourne, 2012). Dickey

(2006) argues that with globalization and the advancement of media, everything has become commercialized, and even women are treated as commodities. Advertisements often portray women as objects of pleasure, emphasizing their physical appearance. Similarly, Simrogh (2003) suggests that women in media are primarily exploited for unjust representation and the sale of goods, with little consideration beyond that. In Pakistan, the television industry is more developed than the film industry, with television series being watched in almost every household, therefore, it has more impact on Pakistani audiences. Moreover, previously, many dramas focused on the evils of society. With globalization, Pakistani dramas have gained popularity in other South Asian countries, making television a significant source of entertainment and influence but also making it more commercialized to attract the audience. However, it is important to recognize that gender bias and stereotypes are influenced by socially constructed gender roles. These can be seen as societal expectations of an individual's behavior based on their perceived gender. Men are typically expected to display composure and assertiveness, as well as dominant characteristics, while women are expected to exhibit more traditionally feminine traits, such as compassion and care (Amanatullah & Tinsley, 2013).

Numerous studies have shown that Pakistani media often depicts women as sensitive, caretakers, and homemakers, while men are frequently portrayed in public roles outside the home as breadwinners. Dramas typically present men as holding decisive power, authority, direction, reasoning, and rationality (Groves et al., 2020; Signorielli, 2011). Female characters generally receive less recognition and acknowledgment compared to their male counterparts. It is rare to see men depicted as domestically involved alongside women; instead, domestic duties are predominantly portrayed as the responsibility of women, often associated with compassion and care.

The social fabric of Pakistani society is patriarchal, where men are considered the breadwinners of the family and, hence, hold all the decisive power in domestic affairs. Women are considered

submissive and often hide under the veil of domestication, neglecting their professional achievements (Rameez Ul Huda & Amber, 2015; Bjursell & Backvall, 2011). While many dramas are female-centric and some promote progressive and gender-sensitive messages, most often, female characters are portrayed as passive and sensitive, reinforcing patriarchal values, whereas orthodox views are frequently challenged and victimized (Sajid & Aleem, 2022, p. 5).

In addition to the traditional roles that challenge women's empowerment and image, another significant challenge prevalent in Pakistani society is the media portrayal of women as mere objects of beauty. This portrayal not only exposes existing mentalities but also perpetuates gender stereotypes, reinforcing the notion that a woman's worth in society is determined by her physical appearance rather than her ability to excel (Ahmed & Wahab, 2019; Manzoor et al., 2016; Rabia et al., 2019). As a result, women are under constant pressure to meet unrealistic standards, which often leads to psychological and emotional abuse.

For a nation such as Pakistan, it is imperative to consistently observe and scrutinize the gender norms, characteristics, and clichéd personas portrayed in its media. This is because Pakistani audiences frequently absorb false information from the media, which unintentionally forms the basis of their "truth" and "perception" of gender roles particularly for females. This is especially risky in Pakistan, where there is frequently little check of what young people see on television or what are the possible psychological effects it might have on it. The media's power and its ability to brainwash vulnerable minds are largely unfettered. Hence, the 'truth' they are being shown becomes their 'truth'.

When television dramas depict men in misogynistic roles and female characters falling in love with such characters, the focus shifts from reasoning and rationality to commercialization. The profound impact of this can have been often underestimated. Although the media is not solely to blame—since societal structures also play a role—women are partly responsible for succumbing to these existing taboos and being influenced by socially constructed standards.

Despite having enormous potential, many women are constrained by these limiting perceptions (Butler, 1999). For instance, a male leader is simply referred to as a leader, without any additional qualifiers, whereas a female leader is often labeled specifically as a "female leader." This distinction suggests that a woman's social attributes, which define her as a woman, are considered before other important attributes such as competence, skills, and knowledge (Ridgeway & Smith-Lovin, 1999). This bias is evident in media coverage. Given the powerful impact of media on our lives, it is undeniable that women are significantly affected by the perceptions conveyed through these platforms.

Theoretical Construct: Cultivation Theory

The methodological construct of this paper is based on 'Cultivation Theory', proposed by George Gerbner in 1967. This theory specifically addresses how the attitudes and beliefs of the

general public are shaped through prolonged exposure to media. According to this theory, television can significantly influence an individual's belief system, especially when it consistently depicts themes of violence, hate, and crime. This impact is particularly noticeable in young individuals, who can internalize these behavioral patterns through continuous exposure, leading to distorted perceptions of gender roles and beauty standards. In the context of this research, 'Cultivation Theory' provides a framework for understanding how Pakistani TV dramas, which often emphasize the beauty and physical appearance of female characters, shape societal attitudes. With the continuous and repetitive portrayal of such roles, an environment is cultivated where media-tailored female roles become socially accepted, potentially having a detrimental impact on women's self-awareness, self-consciousness, and societal expectations.

Research Hypothesis:

The exposure and portrayal of traditional female roles in Pakistani media (TV) leads to gender stereotypes that are detrimental to women's self-

esteem and negatively impact society's perspectives of them.

Independent variables: Pakistani media (TV/Movies)

Dependent Variables: Gender roles and Norms, self-esteem, body image, unrealistic expectations.

Research Methodology:

This research will utilize a mixed-method approach, specifically employing a Sequential Quan- Qual research design. The study gathered data from approximately 205 questionnaires completed by students from various colleges and universities in Lahore. Initially, the target sample consisted of 50 students from each college; however, due to many participants not being residents of Lahore and some being unwilling to complete the questionnaire, the sample size and composition varied. Detailed information regarding this

variation is provided below. For the qualitative component, three in-depth interviews were conducted with clinical psychologists to gain professional insights into their opinions and experiences. They were asked four comprehensive questions related to the portrayal of women in the media, its effects, and how women perceive themselves with the internalization of gender roles in Pakistani media. This combination of quantitative and qualitative data aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research topic.

Forman Christian College	27
Kinnaird College for Women	115
Lahore College for Women	25
Miscellaneous (UMT, USA, GCU, Naheed Medical College)	38

Data Analysis:

Data analysis was conducted through the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data. Thematic analysis was employed to identify key themes from the survey data, which were then

corroborated and expanded upon by insights gained from the in-depth interviews. This integrated approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the research findings.

Results:

Demographic Profile

The demographic profile of this survey primarily consists of respondents aged 20-25, accounting

for 115 individuals, 61% of the total sample. Respondents aged 15-20 comprise 75 individuals,

representing 36.6% of the sample size. The age bracket of 25-30 includes 3 respondents, which is 1.5% of the sample, and there are 2 respondents over 30, making up 1% of the total sample size

portrayed in Pakistani television and movies. A significant number, 63 respondents (30.7%), remained neutral on the issue. Additionally, 24 respondents (11.7%) strongly disagreed that women are appropriately portrayed. A smaller group of 33 respondents (16.1%) agreed that the portrayal is somewhat accurate, while only

Based on the responses to this question, the majority of women, 40% (82 respondents), perceive that the stereotypical portrayal of women reinforces social norms. Additionally, 27.8% (57 respondents) occasionally acknowledged this impact, while 18.5% (38 respondents) strongly agreed with the reinforcement of social norms. A

Q1: To what extent do you believe that women are appropriately portrayed in Pakistani television series and movies?

According to the responses to this question, the majority of respondents, 80 individuals (39%), believe that women are somewhat inaccurately

- Very Inaccurate
- Somewhat Inaccurate
- Neutral
- Somewhat Accurate
- Very Accurate

5 respondents (2.4%) strongly agreed that women are appropriately portrayed in Pakistani dramas.

Q2: How often do you see women portrayed in the media in stereotypical ways, such as submissive roles that reinforce social norms?

- Never
- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Frequently
- Always

significant number, approximately 12.2% (25 respondents), rejected this assumption, and a small fraction, 1.5% (3 respondents), completely refuted it.

Q3: Do you think that the way women are portrayed in the media in Pakistan affects how society views gender roles?

Based on the responses to this question, a significant proportion, approximately 49.8% (102 respondents), agreed that gender roles are strongly influenced by media portrayal. Additionally, 28.8% (59 respondents) strongly agreed with this view. In contrast, 13.2% (27 respondents)

remained neutral. A small portion, 5.9% (12 respondents), disagreed, while 2.4% (5 respondents) strongly disagreed with the assertion.

Q 4: Are there specific TV shows or movies that you feel positively impact the perception of women in Pakistani society?

According to the responses to this question, 120 respondents (58.5%) agreed that there are very few TV shows that positively impact the perception of women in Pakistani society. In contrast, 55 respondents (26.8%) agreed that several dramas have had a positive impact. Additionally, 14 respondents (6.8%) felt that

many dramas positively influence women's perceptions, while 9 respondents (4.4%) completely disagreed, and 7 respondents (3.4%) indicated that they had no opinion on the matter.

Q5: Have you ever experienced pressure from the media to adhere to gender stereotypes?

Based on the responses to this question, a significant proportion, nearly 82 respondents (40%), indicated that they sometimes felt pressure from the media to conform to gender stereotypes. Additionally, 38 respondents (18.5%) reported often feeling pressured, while 34 respondents (16.6%) claimed they never experienced such pressure. Moreover, 44

respondents (21.5%) stated they rarely felt pressured, and a small minority of 7 respondents (3.4%) indicated that they always experienced pressure from the media.

Q6: Do you believe that media plays a role in challenging traditional gender roles in Pakistani society?

Regarding whether media plays a role in challenging traditional gender roles in Pakistani society, 100 respondents (48.8%) agreed it is important. Additionally, 31 respondents (15.1%) strongly agreed with this statement. However, a

significant number, 51 respondents (24.9%), remained neutral. Meanwhile, 19 respondents (9.3%) disagreed, and 4 respondents (2%) strongly disagreed.

Q7: Do you think there is any connection between Pakistani society's expectations for women and the way women are portrayed in the media?

According to the responses to this question, a substantial portion, approximately 101 respondents (49.3%), believe that there is a moderate relationship between Pakistani society's

expectations for women and their portrayal in the media. Additionally, 49 respondents (23.9%) strongly agreed that this relationship is strong. Conversely, 46 respondents (22.4%) felt that there is a weak relationship, while only a small segment, comprising 9 respondents (4.4%), believed there is no relationship between media portrayals of women and societal expectations.

Q8: Have you observed instances where media portrayals have influenced attitudes towards women's roles in your community?

According to the responses to this question, 86 respondents (42%) believe they have observed instances where media portrayals have influenced attitudes toward women's roles in their community. Additionally, 65 respondents (31.7%)

According to the responses to this question, 50 respondents (24.4%) believe that media representations contribute to or challenge prevailing beauty standards for women in Pakistan. Additionally, 41 respondents (20%) remained neutral. Of those surveyed, 35 respondents (17.1%) view that media representations challenge prevailing beauty standards, while 37 respondents (18%) believe that media representations strongly

According to the responses to this question, 57 respondents (27.8%) stated that they have personally experienced changes in self-perception or confidence due to media influence, while 49 respondents (23.9%) reported having been considerably affected. A smaller group, 17 respondents (8.3%), strongly believed that they

frequently observed this phenomenon. Meanwhile, 38 respondents (18.5%) rarely experienced it, and 10 respondents (4.9%) always experienced it. A small portion, consisting of 6 respondents (2.9%), reported never experiencing this influence.

Q9: Do you think media representations contribute to or challenge prevailing beauty standards for women in Pakistan?

contribute to these standards. Finally, 42 respondents (20.5%) feel that media representations strongly challenge the prevailing standards of beauty in Pakistan.

Q10: Have you personally experienced changes in self-perception or confidence due to media influence?

are greatly influenced by the media. However, 49 respondents (23.9%) indicated that they have only slightly experienced such changes. A notable portion, 33 respondents (16.1%), believed that they have not experienced any influence from the media at all.

Q11: How do you think media portrayals impact the overall well-being of women in Pakistan?

According to the responses to this question, 77 respondents (37.6%) believed that media portrayals negatively impact the overall well-being of women in Pakistan, while 15 respondents (7.3%) felt that the media has a very negative impact on women. Interestingly, a significant portion, 90 respondents (43.9%), remained neutral. On the positive side, 17 respondents (8.3%) believed that the media has a positive impact, and only 6 respondents (2.9%) felt that it has a very positive effect.

Discussion & Analysis:

The purpose of this article was to explore the impact of the media's representation of Pakistani women, specifically its effects on gender roles, societal perceptions, mental health, and body image. The study focused on how media portrayals shape these aspects of women's lives and gender norms. A survey was conducted to gather responses from female college and university students and teachers to get their opinions on these trends. Additionally, three in-depth interviews with clinical psychologists were conducted to obtain a more nuanced understanding of the issue. This approach aimed to provide a deeper insight into the role of media in shaping perceptions and reinforcing gender roles in Pakistani society. By triangulating findings from the literature review, survey responses, and interviews, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of the subject. This research underscores the pivotal role of the media and how it shapes societal perspectives, particularly about gender roles, norms, and values. Below are the key themes derived from the data to provide a deeper understanding of the issue.

Theme 1: Media's Role in Shaping Gender Roles:

One of the common themes observed in both the survey and interviews is the strong influence of media in shaping young women's perceptions of gender roles. Both sets of data highlighted that Pakistani media reinforces stereotypical gender roles. According to Question 3 of the survey, 49.8% of respondents agreed that media influences societal perceptions of gender roles, and 28.8% strongly agreed that media shapes specific perceptions associated with women. Stereotypically, the media portrays women in a way that ultimately dictates their roles in society, as agreed by 40% of respondents in Question 2 of the survey.

A similar response was received from two clinical psychologists, who pointed out that media often promotes stereotypical portrayals of women, associating specific behaviors with physical appearance, which limits their roles in society. This reinforces the idea that young women internalize these portrayals, affecting their self-perception. The third psychologist further noted that stereotypical characters in Pakistani dramas often emphasize domestic roles for women, limiting their aspirations beyond homemaking. Women are thus dictated to believe that their roles in productivity and creativity are restricted.

Theme 2: Mental health, Body Positivity and Self-Esteem. The second common theme identified in both the surveys and interviews was the impact of media on the mental health, body positivity, and self-esteem of women. Quantitative data indicated that many respondents believe media representations negatively influence their self-perception. For instance, 37.6% of respondents reported that media portrayals adversely affect their well-being (Question 11), while 27.8% (57 respondents) acknowledged personal experiences

of changes in self-perception or confidence due to media influence. Additionally, 23.9% (49 respondents) stated they were significantly impacted by these portrayals (Question 10).

Interviews with clinical psychologists further validated these findings. One psychologist explained that repeated exposure to stereotypical portrayals can damage self-esteem, particularly among impressionable viewers who tend to compare themselves to idealized media characters. Women from less affluent backgrounds, in particular, may experience diminished confidence when they see themselves reflected in negative media depictions. Another psychologist elaborated on how media often reinforces a mindset where women in toxic relationships accept their circumstances, fostering feelings of helplessness and low self-worth. This underscores the psychological toll persistent stereotypes in media can have, contributing to mental health issues such as anxiety and depression.

However, the third psychologist offered a contrasting perspective, suggesting that repeated exposure to stereotypical portrayals in Pakistani media does not necessarily harm the mental health or self-esteem of young women. Instead of viewing themselves as victims, many women see themselves as resilient and empowered. They develop skills to overcome challenges by imagining how they would respond to similar situations with strength and determination. As a result, these women maintain high self-esteem and reject the 'bechari' (helpless) mindset.

Theme 3: Internalized Misogyny Another common theme identified in both the survey and interviews is the concept of internalized misogyny. The majority of respondents in Questions 5 and 6 believe that media not only perpetuates patriarchal values but also encourages women to internalize these oppressive narratives, with 48.8% (100 respondents) agreeing with this view. Additionally, 18.5% (38 respondents) reported frequently feeling pressured due to media influence.

The first psychologist elaborated on how the media's misogynistic portrayals reinforce harmful gender norms. These norms become deeply embedded in society, shaping women's perceptions and often leading to internalized

misogyny. The second psychologist noted that this internalized misogyny can manifest as women judging or policing other women based on these sexist ideals, thereby perpetuating a cycle of oppression. The third psychologist further expanded on this by explaining that media narratives frequently emphasize toxic relationships between women, such as mother-in-law and daughter-in-law dynamics. This focus leads women to internalize negative behaviors and attitudes towards other women, with media promoting a sense of competition that reinforces internalized misogyny.

Theme 4: Impact on Beauty Standards and Body-consciousness on Women

A recurrent theme identified in both the survey and interviews is the impact of media on beauty standards and body consciousness among women. The data indicate that the media often sets unrealistic beauty standards, which can significantly affect young women's self-esteem. The survey responses reveal a broad consensus on this issue: 49.8% (102 respondents) agreed that media portrayals strongly influence gender roles, with an additional 28.8% (59 respondents) expressing strong agreement. Furthermore, 58.5% (120 respondents) felt that there are very few television shows that positively influence the perception of women in Pakistani society.

The first psychologist noted that media has increasingly promoted unattainable beauty ideals, leading young women to pursue cosmetic surgery and exacerbating socio-economic disparities. These ideals foster dissatisfaction with one's appearance and contribute to diminished self-esteem. The second psychologist emphasized the role of television dramas in perpetuating an obsession with fair skin, straight hair, and slim bodies, which further exacerbates self-esteem issues. Social media intensifies this problem by amplifying these beauty standards and increasing women's concern about their appearance in the eyes of others. The third psychologist corroborated that media frequently showcases edited and photoshopped images, further distorting perceptions of beauty.

Triangulation and Saturation of the Findings:

The primary objective of employing a mixed-method approach is to integrate both qualitative and quantitative data to achieve a comprehensive analysis of the proposed research. This article examines the impact of media on Pakistani women, focusing on their mental health, stereotypical roles, and established beauty standards. The quantitative data collected through surveys from university students indicate a broad consensus among respondents regarding the media's influence on gender roles and beauty standards, illustrating how media functions as an enforcing agent that associates certain stereotypical roles with women. In contrast, the qualitative data from interviews with clinical psychologists offer in-depth professional insights into the psychological manifestations of these effects and their prevalence in society. The integration of findings from both qualitative and quantitative sources has reached a saturation point, underscoring the profound impact of media on gender roles and perceptions of women within Pakistani society.

Conclusion:

In summary, the data collected indicates that media representation of women in Pakistan is strongly associated with the reinforcement of gender stereotypes, internalized misogyny, and the imposition of unrealistic beauty standards. These media portrayals significantly influence young women's self-perception, mental health, and societal roles. According to our theoretical framework, the pervasive presence of media and its deep penetration into Pakistani society contribute to the internalization of these behaviors. The continuous and repetitive depiction of certain female roles creates an environment where media-influenced portrayals become socially accepted, potentially harming women's self-awareness, self-consciousness, and societal expectations. While some women may resist these narratives, the overwhelming majority experience negative psychological effects, leading to a cycle of distress characterized by low self-esteem and adherence to restrictive gender norms. Understanding these dynamics and their long-lasting impact on women's health is crucial for

advocating media reform. Such reforms should aim to present content that fosters positive change in societal gender roles and responsibilities, embraces diversity, and portrays women in empowering and diverse ways.

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